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Gender And School Location As Determinant Of Academic Self- Efficacy Of Secondary School Students In Southwest, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This research investigated gender and school location as determinant of academic self-efficacy of secondary school students in southwest, Nigeria. Literatures were reviewed on gender, school location and academic self-efficacy. The target population comprised all senior secondary school one students in southwest geo political zone of Nigeria. The research design adopted for this study is quasi experimental design. Multi-stage sampling was adopted for this study, at stage 1, purposive sampling technique was used to select 3 states to represent the six states in southwest because they possess similar characteristics. At stage 2, simple random sampling technique was used to select four secondary schools from the states purposively selected. At stage 3, simple random sampling technique was used to select 50 students from each of the 12 schools across the three states to make a total of 600 students. Two research hypotheses were formulated such as; There is no significant joint interaction effect of academic self-efficacy technique treatment and gender on the academic performance of secondary school students which was accepted ($F_{(1,591)} = .312, p > .05, \eta^2 = .001$), thus indicate that gender does not play any joint interaction effect with the treatment on their academic performance. The hypothesis which states There is no significant interaction effect of academic self-efficacy treatment and school location (rural and urban) on the academic performance of secondary school students ($F_{(1,591)} = 13.197, p < .05, \eta^2 = .054$) which was rejected. It was concluded that the school location of secondary school students play significant roles on their academic self-efficacy which thus affect their academic performance. Recommendations are made: The secondary school teachers should be trained on the importance of building academic self-efficacy of the secondary school students so as to enhance their academic performance, the teachers should imbibe the culture of positive reinforcement in order for the students to develop interest on their academic pursuit.

Keywords: Gender, School location, Self-efficacy, Academic Performance, School

INTRODUCTION

No nation can thrive above its level of education because it is an important tool for sporadic self and national development. The quality of education given in any society thus portrays the quality of life in the society especially if the recipients are assimilating and putting into practice through their actions (overt behaviour) the contents of such education (Jasmawi, 2008). The problem of low academic achievement of students in examinations is one of the most challenging problems that faces students as well as teachers which emanated from low academic self-efficacy of students by perceiving themselves as those that cannot perform a particular academic tasks (Burns, VanDerHeyden, & Boice, 2008).

Schunk (2003) and Pajare (2006) expressed that competent behaviour is largely understood in terms of developing relevant knowledge, skills and attitudes, researchers in educational settings are increasingly drawing attention to the role students thoughts and beliefs play in the learning process. Almuammria (2015) opined that the students learning environment such as Rural and Urban areas play an imminent role on their self-efficacy nature because of their thoughts and irrational beliefs towards their academic performances. Schunk (2003) and Pajare (2006) further revealed that self-efficacy is a key element of social cognitive theory which appears to be a significant variable in student's learning because it affects students' motivation and learning.

Academic self-efficacy is a necessary academic construct that emphasizes on the self-courage, self-confidence among other variables to excel in academic endeavour (Jasmawi, 2008). For instance an individual who experiences low self-concept, low self esteem, failure mentality and not seeing any good thing in himself may end up not being able to take risks not to talk of excelling in his or her academic endeavours. Academic self-efficacy refers to an individual's beliefs (conviction) that they can successfully achieve at a designated level on an academic task or attain a specific academic goal (Bandura, 1997; Eccles & Wigfield, 2002, Linnenbrink & Pintrich, 2002).

The issue of students with self-efficacy problem is not only that they fail to achieve academically, but they tend to enter adulthood "illiterate, dependent upon drugs and alcohol, unemployed or under-employed, as a teenage parent dependent on welfare, or adjudicated by the criminal justice system" (Barr & Parrett, 1995). Income and class status have become increasingly determined by educational success. The gap in achievement has shifted steadily from being an indicator of educational inequality to being a direct cause of socioeconomic inequality (Johnson, 2000). Stronge (2007) states that "at-risk students report that teachers do not understand them and that the work is too difficult or boring, fear for their physical safety, they cannot complete homework assignments, do not or cannot participate in extracurricular or social activities, and they get little or no support from home". Of all the factors that affect academic performance of at-risk students, teachers have the most impact on their academic achievement (Parsley & Corcoran, 2003).

Effective teachers of at-risk students have been described as "warm demanders" (Howard, 2002). Their students know that they care for them, but also understand that they expect and will not accept anything but the best from them. These teachers work to ensure that students attend school on a regular basis. Most importantly, they see their students as individuals, not as "poor" students or "minority" students (Stronge, 2007). Self-efficacy is a critical characteristic needed in teachers of at-risk students. Teachers with high efficacy are not intimidated by their students' backgrounds. They do not allow student's home life to interfere with their belief in their student's academic capabilities. They do not allow factors such as poverty, lack of parent participation, and other issues to impact their belief that all students can learn. Instead, these factors are seen as surmountable obstacles and ones that can most definitely be overcome (Stronge, 2007).

In 2002, a group of researchers conducted a study concerning the correlation between teacher involvement (interaction) and student engagement (Tucker, Porter, Reinke, Herman & Ivery, 2002). Findings from the study recommended additional research on the relationship between teacher efficacy and culturally diverse students. The researchers developed a teacher-training program designed to promote teacher efficacy in relation to culturally diverse students. The researchers based their investigation on the findings of Gibson and Dembo (1984). They learned that teachers who believe student learning is influenced by teaching despite home and peer influence and who had confidence in their ability to teach, persisted longer in their teaching efforts, provided greater academic focus in the classroom, gave different types of feedback, and ultimately improved student performance. These teachers persisted because they have confidence in their ability to teach. It postulates that behavior problems and academic failure, as well as pro-social behavior and academic success are significantly influenced by the levels of five significant factors (Tucker, Porter, Reinke., Herman, & , Ivery., 2005) which include: Self-motivation to achieve academic and social success, Perceived self-control over one's

behavior and academic success, self-reinforcement for engaging in social and academic success behaviors, adaptive skills for life success, engagement in success behaviors

Bandura (1986) opined self-efficacy as the capability that is distinctly human (self direction) hence it is a prominent feature of social cognitive theory. Through self-reflection, people make sense of their experiences, explore their own cognition and self, beliefs, engage in self-evaluation, and alter their thinking and behaviors accordingly. Of all the thoughts that affect human functioning, and standing at the very core of social cognitive theory are self efficacy beliefs “people judgments of their capabilities to organize and excuses of action require to attain designated types performances. Self-efficacy beliefs provide the foundation for human motivation, well-being, and personal accomplishment. This is because unless people belief that their actions can produce the outcomes they desires, they have little incentive to act or to persevere in the face of difficulties. Bandura (1997) key contentions as regards the role of self efficacy beliefs in human functioning is that people’s `level of motivation, effective states and actions are based more on what they belief than on what is objectively true, for this reason, how adolescents behave can often be better predicted by the beliefs they hold about their capabilities than by what they are actually capable of accomplishing, for these, self-efficacy perceptions help determine what individuals do with the knowledge and skills they have. Bandura’s self-efficacy as a social construct is a collective system that develop a sense of collective efficiency group which shares belief in it’s capability to attain goals and accomplished desired tasks. For example, schools develop collective beliefs about the capability of their students to learn, of their teachers to teach and otherwise enhance the lives of their students and of their administrators and policymakers to create environments conducive to these tasks, Staples, Sandy, John, Hullard and Christopher (1998) self-efficacy theory suggests that there are four major sources of information used by individuals when forming self-efficacy judgments which are: Personal assessment information that is based on an individual personal accomplishments, previous success raises mastery expectations, while repeated failures lower them, vicarious experience gained by observing others performing activities successfully, this is often referred to as modeling, and it can generate expectations in observers that they can improve their own performance by learning from what they observed, activities where people are led, through suggestion, into believing that they can cope successfully with specific tasks, the adolescents physiological or emotional states influence self-efficacy judgments with respect to specific tasks. Emotional reaction to such tasks (e.g anxiety) can lead to negative judgments of one ability to complete the tasks. Also, stress level can also impart how a person feels about their personal abilities in a particular situation. A person who becomes extremely nervous before speaking in public may develop a weak sense of self-efficacy judgments with respect to specific tasks. Emotional reaction to such tasks can also impart how a person feels about their personal abilities in a particular situation. A person who becomes extremely nervous before speaking in public may develop a weak sense of self-efficacy in this situation.

Statement of the Problem

The recent results of West African Examination Council result that was released via social media on August, 07, 2023 revealed that among the 1, 613,733 candidates who participated in the examination, the results of 262, 803 candidates was withheld due to reported instances of examination malpractices (www.guardian.ng). This indicates that some of them experienced low academic self-efficacy as a result of nefarious activities that they engages in such as examination malpractice, enforcing their teachers to pass them through threatening or intimidation. It was discovered that the male students are more efficacious more than their female counterparts which thus affect their academic performance. The school location has perceived to have significant impact on the secondary school student's self-efficacy because the students in the urban area secondary schools have ample opportunity to learn with modern equipments because the government usual make adequate provisions for them while the reverse is the case with the students in the rural area secondary schools because the government does not put them as priority which thus affects their self-efficacy.

This then calls for an urgent need to help students realize their potentialities and abilities through building their academic self- efficacy to correct their irrational thought and belief of "I cannot make it in an examinations without any assistance". Many secondary school students do not see themselves as individuals that can perform academic tasks without the assistance of their teachers, parents and other significant others

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant joint interaction effect of academic self-efficacy technique treatment and gender on the academic performance of secondary school students
2. There is no significant interaction effect of academic self-efficacy treatment and school location (rural and urban) on the academic performance of secondary school students.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design adopted for this study are pre-test, post-test, control group, quasi-experimental design, while a 2 x 2 x 2 factorial design matrix was utilized. The target population for this study consists of all secondary school students in S.S.S 1 in urban and rural areas of Southwest geo political zone of Nigeria (Oyo, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Lagos and Ekiti state).

The participants for this study comprised of the randomly selected secondary school students in Southwest geo-political zone of Nigeria. While two hundred secondary school students were randomly selected from each state of the randomly selected ones in the Southwest geo-political zone culminating into one thousand, two hundred students altogether. The research adopts multi-stage sampling technique: at stage 1, purposive sampling technique was used to select three states from the six states of the Southwest geo-political zone to represent the whole regions because they have similar characteristics such as common language, gender and school of environments. At stage two, four secondary schools were randomly selected from each of the three states, where two schools were used for experimental group and the other two schools for control group respectively making a total of twelve schools in the three states. Simple random sampling technique was used at stage 3 to select 50 Secondary School Students who are in senior secondary school 1 from each of the schools selected to make a total of 600 secondary school students. The pretest was conducted on the participants to discover their academic self-efficacy level in order to group them into the experimental and the control groups. Academic Self-efficacy scale was a self-developed scale by the researchers. Academic Self-efficacy Scale (QASES) is a self-developed instrument by the researchers. The instrument used for collecting data for this study was a questionnaire tagged (QSES). The questionnaire was developed by the researcher and the items used were reviewed from literatures. It consisted of two sections. Section A entails the demographic information about the respondents while section B contains twenty (20) items which were meant to know the self-efficacy level of the students. The instrument is a four likert instrument with SA – strongly agreed (4Pts.) A – Agreed

(3Pts.), D – Disagree (2Pts.), SD – strongly disagree (1Pts.). The total score for the items is 4points x 20items = 80marks, therefore any respondent that score below 40marks is considered to have low self – efficacy, while those that score above 40marks are considered to have high self – efficacy. Meanwhile, those that score below 40marks was used for the research because they are the main target that the cognitive restructuring instrument would be used to enhance their self-efficacy. This group was divided into experimental and control groups. Where the experimental group was treated with cognitive restructuring strategy.

The content of the instruments validity was ensured by giving it to four experts in the department of test and measurement to establish the content and face validity of the instruments. Test-retest reliability was used by administering the instrument twice after an interval of four weeks to the respondents who are not part of the target population after which the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to ascertain its reliability by correlating the instruments and it yielded 0.79 which makes it reliable for use.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the administration of the instruments were analysed by using the following techniques: Frequency count, Simple percentage and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) were used to test the hypotheses.

RESULTS

This aspect presents the result on gender and school location as determinant of academic self-efficacy of secondary school students in southwest, Nigeria. Two research hypotheses were tested. The demographic data was analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used for the hypotheses to determine the level of significant difference.

Analysis of demographic characteristic of the students

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Respondents by gender

Treatment	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Experimental Group Cognitive Restructuring	300	50.0
Control Group	300	50.0
Total	600	100.0

Table 1 revealed that 300 representing 50.0% of the participants were from Experimental Group academic self-efficacy while 300 of them or 50.0% were from Control Group. Therefore, the above result implies that equal number and percentage of secondary school students were used for Experimental Group Academic self-efficacy and Control Group respectively for the study.

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Respondents by gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	258	43.0
Female	342	57.0
Total	600	100.0

Table 2 revealed that 342 representing 57.0% of the participants were female, 258 of them or 43.0% were male. Therefore, the above result implies that majority of participants were females used for the study.

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Respondents by location

Location	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Urban Area	475	79.2
Rural Area	125	20.8
Total	600	100.0

The result from table 3 depicts that 475 representing 79.2% of the participants were from the urban areas schools while 125 representing 20.8% were from rural areas schools. The result implies that the respondents from urban areas schools were more than their counterparts.

Hypotheses

Table 4: ANCOVA Summary of Academic self-efficacy technique on the academic self- efficacy of secondary school students

Dependent Variable: Post-Test Academic performance						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	218823.331 ^a	8	27352.916	2607.282	.000	.972
Intercept	1640.053	1	1640.053	156.330	.000	.209
Treatment	5110.511	1	5110.511	487.134	.000	.452
Gender	17.882	1	17.882	1.705	.192	.003
Location	39.628	1	39.628	23.777	.023	.064
Pre	27191.948	1	27191.948	2591.939	.000	.814
Treatment * Gender	3.272	1	3.272	.312	.577	.001
Treatment * Location	33.538	1	33.538	13.197	.043	.054
Treatment * Gender * Location	105.586	2	52.793	5.032	.007	.167
Error	6200.163	591	10.491			
Total	2367300.000	600				
Corrected Total	225023.493	599				

a. R Squared = .972 (Adjusted R Squared = .972)

Ho¹ There is no significant interaction effect of academic self-efficacy technique treatment and gender on the academic performance of secondary school students.

From table 4, it was shown that there was no significant interaction effect of academic self-efficacy technique treatment and gender on the academic self- efficacy of secondary school students ($F_{(1,591)} = .312$, $p > .05$, $\eta^2 = .001$). The null hypothesis is therefore accepted. This means that there is no significant interaction effect of academic self-efficacy technique treatment and gender on the academic performance of secondary school students.

Ho⁴ There is no significant interaction effect of academic self-efficacy treatment and school location (rural and urban) on the academic performance of secondary school students.

From table 4, it was shown that there is significant interaction effect of academic self-efficacy treatment and school location (rural and urban) on the academic performance of secondary school students ($F_{(1,591)} = 13.197$, $p < .05$, $\eta^2 = .054$). The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This means that there is significant interaction effect of academic self-efficacy treatment and school location (rural and urban) on the academic performance of secondary school students.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The hypothesis 1 which state that there is no significant interaction effect of academic self-efficacy technique treatment and gender on the academic performance of secondary school students was accepted because the F-value of 0.312 is less than 0.00, $P > 0.05$ which means that there was no significant interaction effect of academic self-efficacy technique treatment and gender on the academic self-efficacy of secondary school students, this is in tandem with Niepel et. al (2002) who opined that the correlation

between academic self - concept and achievement was irrelevant to gender. This indicates that gender does not play significant role on the academic self-efficacy as a result of cognitive restructuring tool. The hypothesis 2 which state that there is no significant interaction effect of academic self-efficacy treatment and school location (rural and urban) on the academic performance of secondary school students was rejected because F-value of 13.197 was greater than the Partial Eta Square 0.054, $P < 0.05$ which means that there was significant interaction effect of cognitive restructuring treatment and school location (rural and urban) on the academic self –efficacy of secondary school students, this corroborated the research carried out by Aguillon et. al (2020) who viewed that students possessing higher academic self- concept in the active learning environment were more likely to show a higher sense of self-efficacy.

CONCLUSION

It was discovered from the research work that academic performance of secondary school students in the southwest geo political zone of Nigeria could be enhanced through academic self-efficacy which will enable them to boost their academic performance. It was concluded from the research that gender, school location amongst other factors enhances their academic performance. The result depicted that academic self-efficacy tool (treatment) makes the students to develop interest on learning in the school which thus play tremendous roles on building their academic performance. It was observed that the poor academic performance manifested by the students in the control group was premised on their low academic self-efficacy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made based on the outcome of the findings:

1. The secondary school teachers should be trained on the importance of building academic self-efficacy of the secondary school students so as to enhance their academic performance.
2. The teachers should imbibe the culture of positive reinforcement in order for the students to develop interest on their academic pursuit.
3. The parents /guardians should be motivating their wards at home by bringing out the best from them
4. The teachers should teach the students with fairness and equity without being gender biased.
5. The government should provide adequate infrastructural facilities needed for effective teaching to both rural and urban secondary schools.
6. The students must be trained on the concept of being resilience to confront any academic challenge

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REFERENCES

- Aguillon S. M., Siegmund G.-F., Petipas R. H., Drake A. G., Cotner S., Ballen C. J. (2020). Gender differences in student participation in an active-learning classroom. *CBE—Life Sci. Educ.* 19.
- Ahmed, W., Minnaert, A., Kuyper, H., & van der Werf, G., (2011). Reciprocal relationships between math self-concept and math anxiety. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 22, 385-389. Retrieved from <http://www.journals.elsevier.com/learning-and-individual-differences/>
- Allington, R. L., (2002). What I've learned about effective reading instruction. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 83, 740-747.
- Almuammria, M., (2015).The impact of the environment in enhancing the academic achievement of students. *Scientific Library*. Annual Meeting of the California Council on Teacher Education, (Fall 2001).

- Bandura, A., (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review*.84 (2): 191–215.
- Bandura, A., (1988). *Organizational Application of Social Cognitive Theory*. *Australian Journal of Management*.13 (2): 275–302.
- Bandura, Albert; Vittorio Caprara, Gian; Barbaranelli, Claudio; Gerbino, Maria; Pastorelli, Concetta, (2003). *Role of Affective Self-Regulatory Efficacy in Diverse Spheres of Psychosocial Functioning*. *Child Development*.74: 769–782.
- Beck, S., (2011). Tokens. Retrieved from www.appstate.edu on 24th January, 2015.
- Brophy, J., (1983). Research on Self Fulfilling Prophecy and Teacher Expectations. *Journal of Educational Psychology*.75 (3).631-651.
- Burns, M. K., VanDerHeyden, A. M., &Boice, C. H. (2008). Best practices in intensive Academic interventions. In A. Thomas & J. Grimes (Eds.), *Best practices in school psychology*. 35, 1151-1162.
- Ferguson, R. F., (2003). Teacher perceptions and expectations and the Black-White Test score gap. *Urban Education*, 38(4), 460-507.
- Gibson, S. & Dembo, M. (1984). Teacher Efficacy: A Construct Validation. *Journal of Educational Psychology*. 76, 569-582.
- Goddard, Roger.; Goddard, Yvonne., (2001). A multilevel analysis of the relationship between teacher and collective efficacy in urban schools. *Teaching and Teacher Education*.
- Jazmawi, A., (2008). *Underachievement and Low Success Rate of Jordanian Students in Secondary Schools, Home Economics*. Jordan
- Johnson, R. D., & Marakas, G. M. (2000). Research report: The role of behavioral modeling in computer skills acquisition: Toward refinement of the model. *Information Systems Research*, 11(4),402–417.
- Kerlinger, F. N. & Lee, H. B. (2000). *Foundations of behavioural research*. Wardsworth Publisher. USA.
- Manthey, G. (2006). Collective efficacy: Explaining school achievement. *Leadership*, 36 (3), 23-36.
- Marzano, R. J., Pickering, D. J., & Pollock, J. E. (2001). *Classroom instruction that works: Research-based strategies for increasing student achievement*. Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Muijs, D., & Reynolds, D., (2002). Teachers’ beliefs and behaviors: What really matters? *Journal of Classroom Interaction*, 37(2), 3-15
- Nelson, J. M., & Harwood, H. (2011). Learning disabilities and anxiety: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 44(1), 3–17.
- Niepel C., Marsh H. W., Guo J., Pekrun R., Möller J. (2022). Revealing dynamic relations between mathematics self-concept and perceived achievement from lesson to lesson: An experience-sampling study. *J. Educ. Psychol.* 114, 1380–139
- Osborne, J. W. & Walker, C. (2006). Stereotype threat, identification with academics and withdrawal from school: Why the most successful students of color might be most likely to withdraw. *Educational Psychology*, 2(4), 563-577.
- Pajares, M. F., (1996). Self-efficacy beliefs in academic settings. *Review of Educational Research*, 66 (4), 543-578.
- Parsley, K. & Corcoran, C. (2003). The classroom teacher’s role in preventing school failure. *Kappa Delta Pi Record*, 39(2), 84-87.
- Podell, & Soodak. (1993). Teacher efficacy and bias in special education referrals. *Journal of Educational Research*, 86, 247-253.
- Samer, M. A. & Mohammed, A. B., (2015). *Low academic achievement: Causes and language results. Theory and practice in language studies*. Jordan.

- Scharlach, T. D., (2008). These kids just aren't motivated to read: The influence of pre service teachers' beliefs on their expectations, instruction, and evaluation of struggling readers. *Literacy Research and Instruction*, 47, 158-173.
- Scherrer V., Preckel F. (2019). Development of motivational variables and self-esteem during the school career: a meta-analysis of longitudinal studies. *Rev. Educ. Res.* 89, 211–258.
- Schunk, D. K., (2003). "Self-Efficacy for Reading and Writing: Influence of Modeling, Goal-Setting, and Self-Evaluation". *Reading and Writing Quarterly*.19: 159–172.
- Staples, D., Sandy, John, S., Hulland & Christopher, A. H. (1998). *Journal of Computed - Meditated*, 3(4).
- Stronge, J. H., (2007). *Qualities of effective teachers*. Alexandria, Virginia: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Sungur. S, Kahraman, N. (2011). The contribution of motivational beliefs to students' metacognitive strategy use. *Egitim ve Bilim*, 36(160):3.
- Thompson, B. R., (2004). Equitable measurement of school effectiveness. *Urban Education*, 39(2), 200-229.
- Tucker, C. M., Porter, T., Reinke, W. M., Herman, & C. K, Ivery, (2005). Promoting teacher efficacy for working with culturally diverse students. *Preventing School Failure*, 50(1), 29-33.
- Woolfolk, H. A. & Spero, R. B. (2005). Changes in teacher efficacy during the early years of teaching: A Comparison of four measures. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 21, 343-356.
- Zelazo, P. D. & Lyons, K. E. (2012). The potential benefits of mindfulness training in early childhood: A developmental social cognitive neuroscience perspective. *Child Development Perspectives*, 6(2) 154–160.